

Causes and Outcome of Acute Kidney Injury on Hospitalized Patients

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) is a common disorder worldwide with severe morbidity, mortality and cost. We conducted a one-year prospective study in a tertiary care center of Nepal to find out causes and cause specific outcome of AKI in hospitalized patients.

Methods: Total 83 patients with AKI were included in the study. Causes of AKI, namely;

- Sepsis
- Hypovolemia
- Others(Intrinsic renal disease and Drugs/Toxins) were studied in this study.

The following cause specific outcomes of AKI were also studied in this study:

- Complete recovery
- Partial recovery
- ICU requirement
- Hemodialysis requirement &
- Death

Results: Hypovolemia was the most common cause of AKI [(N=38(45.78%)], followed by Sepsis[(N=32(38.55%)] and Others[(N=13(15.66%), which included patients with intrinsic renal disease and toxins mediated AKI]. Total 54(65.06%) patients have complete recovery. Total 18 patients (21.6%) had partial recovery. Total 46 patients (55.4%) had ICU requirement, 17 patients (20.48%) had hemodialysis requirement. Overall in-hospital mortality was 11 (13.25%). Regarding outcome, hypovolemia has the highest complete recovery (68.4%) followed by sepsis (65.6%) and others (53.8%). Sepsis has the highest mortality (18.7%) and highest ICU requirement (84.3%). In ‘Others’ group mortality was 0 and had highest partial recovery (46.1%).

Conclusions: Hypovolemia is the most common cause of AKI and have highest complete recovery. Patients with sepsis has highest ICU requirement and the mortality.

Keywords: Acute Kidney Injury; Sepsis; Hypovolemia

INTRODUCTION

Since his first definition of AKI by Homer W. Smith in the fifties^[1], more than 30 different definitions have been used^[2], with incidence ranging from 5%^[3] to 25%^[4]. Since 2004, three definitions, based on serum creatinine and urine output; RIFLE^[5] & AKIN^[6] respectively, and the actual KDIGO classification^[7] have been proposed. AKI is defined as an absolute increase in serum creatinine by 0.3 mg/dL or more within 48 hours or a relative increase of at least 1.5 times baseline that is known or presumed to have occurred within 7 days^[7]. It is a syndrome that rarely has a sole and distinct pathophysiology. Many patients with AKI have a mixed aetiology where the presence of sepsis, ischaemia and nephrotoxicity often co-exist and complicate recognition and treatment^[8]. Conventionally, causes of AKI have been classified into three broad categories:^[9]

- Pre Renal: Due to inadequate renal plasma flow, which includes any insult leading to Hypovolemia and Hypoperfusion. Causes of volume depletion include hemorrhage (eg, from trauma), GI losses, excessive diuresis, and extravascular space sequestration (eg, pancreatitis, burns, and peritonitis).^[10]
- Intrinsic Renal: Due to diseases affecting renal glomeruli, tubules, interstitium and vasculature. The most common causes of intrinsic AKI are sepsis, ischemia, and nephrotoxins, both endogenous and exogenous.^[9] The potential sites of injury are the tubules, interstitium, vasculature, and glomeruli.^[10]
- Post Renal: Due to diseases leading to obstruction in the pathway of unidirectional urinary excretion and resulting into increased retrograde hydrostatic pressure.^[10]

The concept of Acute Renal Failure (ARF) has undergone significant re-examination in recent years. Traditionally, emphasis was given to the most severe acute reduction in kidney function, as manifested by severe azotaemia and often by oliguria or anuria.^[8] As many patients with AKI have a mixed aetiology where the sepsis, ischaemia and nephrotoxicity often co-exist and as the syndrome is quite common among patients without critical illness, it is essential that health care professionals, particularly those without specialisation in renal disorders, detect it promptly.^[8]

In the short term, AKI is associated with an increased length of hospital stay, health care costs, and in-hospital mortality. Its impact extends into the long term, with AKI being associated with increased risks of cardiovascular events, progression to chronic kidney disease (CKD), and long-term mortality.^[11] The incidence of AKI has increased in the past few decades, which might reflect the impact of the increased recognition of this diagnosis and improvements in patient care, namely through improvements in dialytic care, the availability of less nephrotoxic drugs, and a decrease in the use of dopamine and diuretics.^[12]

On average, AKI is present in 5% of patients admitted in hospital and will develop in 25% of patients admitted in Intensive Care Unit (ICU).^[10] A large variation is reported in the disease prevalence (1-25%) and mortality (15-60%). The reported prevalence of AKI in United States ranges from 1% (CA-AKI) to 7% (HA-AKI) of total hospital admissions.^[2] The difficulties of defining the incidence of AKI are especially notable when one searches for data on developing countries the place of residence of more than half of the world's population. No nationwide collection systems are available and data from isolated centers are not based on the current AKI definition. From South Africa, Seedat and Nathoo reported an incidence of 20 cases per year per million population; in Brazil, Noronha et al reported an incidence of 7.9 cases per 1000 hospital admissions and in North India, Jha and Chugh reported a yearly incidence of 6.4/1000 admissions. New definitions of AKI make it necessary to again revisit this issue with unified criteria.^[13]

A study done in Nepal which was published in 2005, found that among 45 patients included, the most common cause of AKI was gastroenteritis (22%), followed by sepsis (20 %). Out of 45 patients, complete recovery was seen in 64.4%, mortality in 22.2%, partial recovery in 4.4%, progression to CKD in 4.4%. Another 4.4% left the hospital against medical advice. Criteria for diagnosis of acute renal failure was acute deterioration in renal function with serum creatinine more than 2 mg/dl and presence of normal sized kidneys or hydronephrotic kidneys with normal cortical thickness on ultrasonography. Chronic renal failure and acute on chronic renal failure were excluded from the study.^[14]

Since AKI can lead to mortality and complications like CKD, identification of risk factors, etiologies and cause specific outcome will help to enhance patient safety.^[2] Knowing the cause and possible outcome helps to stratify the high risk patients and to provide effective treatment as many causes are reversible if treated effectively and timely.^[4] This study will provide an idea about the possible causes and the cause specific outcome in our setting. The information thus obtained can help us to stratify the high-risk patient with possible worse outcome and help us to timely direct the effective treatment as many causes are reversible.

METHODOLOGY:

This study was single centered cross sectional analytical study conducted at Patan Academy of Health Sciences(PAHS), a tertiary hospital in Nepal, from August 2019 to July 2020. Approval of study was obtained from the Institutional Committee (IRC) of PAHS. Consent was taken from all the participants before enrolling in the study.

- General Objective:
 1. To determine the cause specific outcomes of AKI in hospitalized patients.
- Specific objectives:
 1. To find out causes (Hypovolemia, Sepsis and others(intrinsic renal disease and toxins)) of AKI
 2. To determine the cause specific outcome (Mortality, Haemodialysis requirement, ICU requirement, Complete Recovery & Partial Recovery) of AKI within time of discharge or within 2 weeks if patient hasn't recovered completely.

Total 91 participants with AKI were included initially among them, 8 patients lost the follow up, so total 83 patients with age 18 years and above, admitted on Medicine Department(Medical Ward, MICU, Step down ward, Geriatric ward) were included in the study. Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease(CKD), pregnant patients, and obstructive uropathy were excluded from the study.

All patients with Acute Kidney Injury admitted to medicine ward were subjected to clinical evaluation and relevant investigations (Complete Blood Count, Random Blood Sugar, Blood Urea, Serum Creatinine, Serum Sodium and Potassium, Urine Routine Examination, USG abdomen and pelvis). Chronic kidney disease were ruled out with the help of baseline creatinine, duration of illness and USG findings(decreased kidney size and loss of Corticomedullary differentiation)

AKI was defined in the study with KDIGO criteria as follows;^[7]

1. Absolute increase in serum creatinine by more than or equal to 0.3mg/dl within 48 hours, or
2. Increase in serum creatinine to ≥ 1.5 times baseline result (as per laboratory report within 7 days prior to presenting to hospital), which is known or presumed to have occurred within the prior seven days, or

3. Urine volume < 0.5ml/kg/hr for six hours

If baseline creatinine is not known, elevation in creatinine more than 1.5mg/dl (at the time of presentation to hospital) was taken for inclusion. In cases of unknown baseline creatinine value like in our setup relevant cut off value has been taken in other studies also.^[13,14,15] Those patients who failed to attain complete recovery during hospital admission period were only followed up after 2 weeks or in the first follow up.

Complete recovery

If serum creatinine returns to normal (≤ 1.5) within time of hospital admission or within 2 weeks after discharge (first follow up).

Partial recovery

If serum creatinine decreases towards baseline but is still > 1.5 within time of hospital stay or within 2 weeks after discharge (first follow up). Those patients whose creatinine is > 1.5 during the hospital stay but has decreased to lower than or equal to that in first follow up are considered to have complete recovery.

Sepsis is defined with q SOFA criteria; more than or equal to 2 points in patients who are suspected to have infectious pathology.^[16]

1. Respiration rate (RR) more than or equal to 22
2. Altered mentation
3. SBP less than or equal to 100 mmHg

Hypovolemia is defined as:^[13]

1. Decrease in blood pressure to less than 90/60 mmHg
2. Clinical signs of volume depletion
 - a. Tachycardia (Heart Rate > 100 beats per minute)
 - b. Postural hypotension (fall in systolic blood pressure of more than 20mmhg and/or fall in diastolic blood pressure of more than 10mmhg within 2 to 5 minutes of standing after 5 minute period of supine rest)
 - c. Dry mucous membrane
 - d. Decreased urine output

Toxins/ Drugs:

When there is temporal relation of administration/ingestion/injection/inhalation of drugs or toxin (which is known to be Nephrotoxic) in absence of other causative mechanism.

Data were entered in MS Excel and epi info version 7.2.2 and analysis was done in epi info version

7.2.2. Normality of data was tested by comparing a histogram of the sample data to a normal probability curve and using Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test. Comparison of outcome or any other variables between two groups was done by using chi-squared test. For comparison between more than 2 groups one-way ANOVA test or Kruskal Wallis test as appropriate was used. A P-value of 0.05 or less was considered significant.

RESULT

Total 83 patients were included in the study. 46.9% were male and 53.1% were female. The median age of the study population was 55(41-71), 56(32-48) and 38(32-48) years respectively for sepsis, hypovolemia and others group. Overall median age was 54(42-67) years. The age group of 60-69 have highest number of patients N=19(22.89%).

Among the baseline clinical parameters, serum Sodium level and Systolic Blood Pressure at presentation were statistically significant. Patients on 'Others' group have relatively lower serum sodium level at presentation 132.76 ± 2.89 (P value=0.02). Similarly patients with sepsis presented with lower systolic blood pressure 81.25 ± 31.19 (P value=0.00). Hypovolemia is the most common cause of AKI. 38 patients had AKI due to hypovolemia(45.78%); followed by sepsis N=32(38.55%) and 'Others' N=13(15.66%). Regarding outcome, hypovolemic patients have highest complete recovery N=26(68.4%) followed by sepsis N=21(65.6%) and Others N=7(53.81%). Patients with sepsis have highest ICU requirement N=27(84.37%) and also the highest mortality. Mortality was highest in sepsis group N=6(18.75%) followed by hypovolemia N=5(13.1%) and Others N=0.

Statistical comparison of outcome among three groups (Sepsis, Hypovolemia and Others) showed that Sepsis has statistically significant higher number of ICU requirement N=27(84.37%).

Total mortality was 13.25% (N=11), and overall complete recovery was seen in 54 patients (65.06%). Complete recovery was highest in Hypovolemia group N=54 (65.06%). Partial recovery was highest in Others group (68.4%). Patients with Sepsis had highest ICU requirement (84.3%). Also the hemodialysis requirement was highest in Sepsis group (31.2%). Mortality was also highest in the Sepsis group (18.7%).

Table 1: Baseline Clinical and Demographic characteristics

	Sepsis	Hypovolemia	Others	P value
Age(median(IQR))	55(41-71)	56(48-67)	38(32-48)	0.005
Sex	Male(%)	16(50)	21(55.2)	0.09
	Female(%)	16(50)	17(44.7)	
Creatinine on presentation (Mean±SD)	2.89±1	2.3±0.88	2.5±1.2	0.10
Potassium on presentation	4.61±1.02	4.17±0.79	4.6±0.84	0.10
Sodium on presentation	138.71±6.79	136.05±7.35	132.76±2.89	0.02
Systolic BP on presentation	81.25±31.19	92.27±12.15	131.53±33.12	0.00

Table 2: Cause Specific Outcome

Number of patients	Complete recovery	Partial recovery	ICU requirement	Hemodialysis requirement	Death
Sepsis(N=32)	21(65.6%)	5(15.6%)	27(84.37%)	10(31.25%)	6(18.75%)
Hypovolemia(N=38)	26(68.4%)	7(18.4%)	14(36.4%)	5(13.15%)	5(13.1%)
Others(N=13)	7(53.8%)	6(46.1%)	5(38.4%)	2(15.3%)	0

Table 3: Statistical analysis; Cause versus Outcome

Outcome	Sepsis	Hypovolemia	Others	P value
Complete Recovery	21(65.6%)	26(68.4%)	7(53.8%)	0.6
ICU requirement	27(84.3%)	14(36.4%)	5(38.4%)	0.001
Hemodialysis requirement	10(31.2%)	5(13.1%)	2(15.3%)	0.18
Death	6(18.7%)	5(13.1%)	0	0.28

DISCUSSION

Acute kidney injury (AKI), once viewed predominantly as a self-limited and reversible condition, is now recognized as a growing problem associated with significant risks of adverse long-term health outcomes. Many cohort studies have established important relationships between AKI and subsequent risks of recurrent AKI, hospital re-admission, morbidity and mortality from cardiovascular disease and cancer, as well as the development of chronic kidney disease and end-stage kidney disease.^[17] Acute kidney injury (AKI) is one of the most frequent organ failure encountered in intensive care units (ICU).^[18] Moreover, AKI has been repeatedly associated with poor long-term outcomes.^[19]

Moreover the end of 2010s has been marked by the publication of several studies that highlighted an association between AKI and subsequent CKD occurrence. Wald et al. have compared 3,769 to 13,598 matched patients treated or not treated with renal replacement therapy (RRT) in ICU and observed a higher incidence of end-stage renal disease with RRT (2.63 vs. 0.91/100 patient-years, hazard ratio = 3.23 [2.70–3.86]).^[20] Interestingly, patients who fully recover at hospital discharge remain at risk of CKD one year afterwards, particularly in the case of subsequent episodes of AKI during the ICU stay.^[21] Current understanding is that an acute episode leaves an imprint (which is expected to be, biologically, of epigenetic nature) able to promote renal fibrosis.^[22]

In several extensive large cohort studies, AKI has been associated with an increased risk of a cardiovascular events,^[23] especially heart failure. In a recently published meta-analysis, Otudayo et al. reported a 58%, 40%, and 15% increased risk of heart failure, myocardial infarction, and stroke, respectively.^[24] Mechanisms leading to cardiovascular events are not elucidated so far. Accelerated atherosclerosis might be a contributing factor.^[25]

As there is a paucity of data on the aetiologies and the outcome of AKI on hospitalised patients especially in our like developing country^[13] this study has given us insight about the causes and outcome of AKI. The median (IQR) age of the present study population is 55(41-71),56(48-67) and 38(32-48) respectively for Sepsis, Hypovolemia and Others category respectively. Overall median age is 54(42-67) Similar study conducted in India by Mohammad ZA et al found median age of 55 years in overall AKI patients which is similar to the result of this study.^[15] Our study showed hypovolemia as the most common cause of AKI(45.78%) followed by sepsis(38.55%). Study conducted in Nepal by Khakurel, S et al found Gastroenteritis as the most common cause of AKI(22.2%), followed by sepsis, though the group wise outcome was not studied in this study.^[14] Study conducted by Mohammad et al found Sepsis to be the most common cause of AKI(31.9%).^[15]

This study showed overall mortality of 13.25%. Previous study done in Nepal^[14] found overall mortality of 22%, which is higher than the present study. Improved overall survival can be attributable to early aggressive treatment. This study found highest mortality in sepsis group (18.7%) A similar result with mortality in 16-20% was observed in a study conducted in Indian population by Goldberg R et al.^[26] Notably our study showed that Sepsis has the highest probability of requiring ICU admission in patients with AKI(84.3%) which is statistically significant.

LIMITATIONS

- a. Definition of AKI had to base on arbitrary serum creatinine cutoff due to unknown baseline
- b. As this study has many variables in outcome analysis, the sample size is the limiting factor, due to which this study might have failed to get statistically significant result of all the outcome variables
- c. Also the higher proportion of patients requiring ICU in sepsis can be attributable to non AKI causes too. So ICU requirement may not be due to AKI only which might have confounded the result.
- d. Due to short followup period, long term outcome of patients with partial recovery could not be traced.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- Hypovolemia is the commonest cause of AKI as per this study and has highest complete recovery.
- Sepsis has the highest mortality.
- Sepsis has highest probability of requiring ICU which is statistically significant.
- Hypovolemic patients when presents with AKI should be treated promptly as they have greatest chance of complete recovery.
- As patients with sepsis related AKI, have high likelihood of requiring ICU and high risk of mortality so should be treated promptly or needed to be referred early especially from rural health care facilities, where higher dependency treatment units are available so as to prevent mortality.

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